
PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL COMPETENCIES AS CORRELATE OF TEACHERS' ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated principals' managerial competencies as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 269 principals in 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Census sampling technique was used since the entire 269 principals were studied because it is relatively small and manageable. Two sets of instruments titled Principals' Managerial Competencies Scale (PMCS) and Teachers' Organizational Behaviour Scale (TOBS) were used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts, two were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach's Alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of items in the instruments which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.77 and 0.84 for two clusters of PMCS with overall reliability index of 0.81, while 0.84 was obtained for TOBS. The researcher with five research assistants collected data for the study using the direct administration and retrieval method and 97% return was recorded. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer research questions and test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that principals' decision-making and motivational competencies have strong and significant relationship with teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should offer annual financial supports to principals for period of at least two years to enable them enroll in short leadership courses on decision-making competency to refresh their knowledge of making informed decisions that facilitate organizational behaviour of teachers.

Keywords: Principals, Managerial Competencies, Teachers, Organizational Behaviour, Decision-Making Competency, Motivational Competency

Introduction

Every society can be transformed through education, which is why it is highly valued. Education is an essential tool for improving the intelligence, shaping personality, building noble character and imparting skills needed by individuals to prepare them for various roles in life and also make significant contributions toward the progress of the society. One of the crucial stages of learning opportunities offered to students is secondary education.

Secondary education offers learning opportunities to students to acquire skills and knowledge which enable them to reflect upon their aspirations for advanced studies and making future career choice. Agbo and Eleberi (2025) noted that secondary education is designed for value orientation, strengthening of skills and advancing knowledge of holders of the Basic Education Certificates which prepare them for education of a higher level. Secondary education is designed to produce informed and responsible citizens with a sense of respect for values and dignity of labour in the society. Okafor, Nnebedum and Oshia (2025a) opined that secondary education is the learning opportunities offered to students after basic education to equip them with skills and knowledge for preparation of future endeavours, further educational pursuit in higher institutions and making meaningful contributions toward overall societal progress. Okafor et al added that secondary education consolidates the foundation lays by basic education to help foster intellectual development, cultivates critical thinking, improve culture of inquiry and enhance creativity among students. The leader of a secondary school is the principal.

A principal is the administrative head who plans, organizes and directs daily activities of a secondary school. The principal is the administrator who is saddled with the responsibility of planning, delegating and getting things through members of staff to attain primary goals and objectives of a secondary school. According to Adiotomre (2025), a principal is the leader who is tasked with directing, supporting and guiding members of staff to carry out work activities in a secondary school. The principal is the chief administrator who is responsible for making use of the available resources to executive managerial tasks for attainment of predetermined goals. Okafor, Nnebedum and Oshia (2025a) described a principal as the chief executive officer who directs and oversees the daily activities of staff to ensure smooth operations of a secondary school. The principals could ensure that the available resources are utilized to attain set goals through display of managerial competencies.

Managerial competencies are skills to perform administrative tasks and functions within an organization. Obi, Ogbunode and Chukwudolue (2022) defined managerial competencies as the possession of necessary skills to effectively manage resources for enhancing staff productivity in an organization. Managerial competencies encompass traits, expertise and behaviours that allow administrators to perform their responsibilities towards attainment of predetermined goals. It is the skills that enable principals to lead and oversee the daily operations of secondary schools. Eze (2024) described managerial competencies as the knowledge, skills and abilities that principals need to effectively oversee and manage the affairs of their school. Operationally, managerial competencies are knowledge, skills, attitude, traits and experience acquired by school administrators for handling available resources to attain predetermined goals and objective.

There are several competencies that could enable principals to succeed in managing affairs of secondary schools. Odu-Dikoro (2022) asserted that managerial competencies include team-building, planning, interpersonal relations, supervision, motivational and communication competencies. Alysa and Dinah (2020) highlighted managerial competencies

to include: interpersonal relation competency, decision-making competency, analytical competency, empathy competency and motivational competency. The interest of this study is on decision-making and motivational, competencies because some teachers exhibit undesirable behaviour probably due to the fact that some principals are incompetent of making good decisions and motivating teachers to create healthy work atmosphere.

Decision-making competency is the ability to identify, evaluate and choose the best among alternative solutions to a given problem. Decision-making competency as described by Wordah and Ekwesianya (2020), is the capacity for identifying and selecting a course of action to solve a problem or take advantage of an opportunity. It is the ability to choose preferred course of actions in tackling challenges. Samancı and Mazlumoglu (2023) asserted that decision-making competency is the ability to select one option among different alternatives in its most general form. They added that decision-making competency allows for purposeful actions and realistic evaluations of options by enabling individuals to make more effective decisions. Decision-making competency includes the ability to develop alternative plans, avoid procrastination, seek advice and choose best alternative solutions to a given problem. Oredein and Opatunde (2023) noted that decision-making competency include: time management, emotional intelligence, problem-solving confidence, flexibility, creativity thinking, evaluating risks, weighing pros and cons, analytical and critical thinking, information gathering and analysis amongst others. It is through decision-making competency that principals could identify the nature of the problem and determine appropriate alternatives to solve it in secondary schools. The implementation of final decisions could be enhanced by boosting the morale of teachers to work hard. One of the means of boosting the morale of teachers is through motivational competency.

Motivational competency is the ability to propel members of staff to exhibit desirable behaviour towards the attainment of set goals. Ibezim (2024) asserted that motivational competency which involves appropriate use of monetary and non-monetary rewards could boost the morale of teachers to effectively discharge their duties with little or no supervision. The author added that motivational competence could be applied by principals to make teachers satisfied and dedicated to discharging their duties in secondary schools. Motivational competency is the skills for providing financial and emotional supports which inspires a worker to achieve a desired purpose. Motivational competency is applied through showing concern towards staff's wellbeing, adequate compensation and promotion to enhance their effectiveness and efficiency in the workplace. Motivational competency is the skill to offer full appreciation for work well done, provide good working conditions; praise dedicated staff, provide opportunity for staff professional development, show special recognition for goal attainment and give sympathetic assistance to staff facing professional and personal problems. Motivated teachers are likely to exhibit good organizational behaviour.

Organizational behaviour is a series of actions and attitudinal patterns towards the accomplishment of job duties. As defined by Pacino and Baguio (2024), organizational behaviour is how individuals interact and act within an organization, such as a school or business, and how these actions shape the organization's overall performance. Organizational behaviour is the reaction of staff towards various aspects of their work roles and environment to execute their daily tasks to achieve set goals. Organizational behaviour is defined by Adisa, Suleiman, Ishola and Muchilwa (2021), as the work attitude displayed by members of staff at all times to encourage efficient running of the organization and subsequently lead to the attainment of the goals. Organizational behaviour is the attitude of staff towards their work conditions and situations. Operationally, organizational behaviour is the conduct and

approach in which staff deal with colleagues, learners and responsibilities in the work environment.

Teachers' organizational behaviour is displayed by their loyalty to school, dedication and commitment to their work. Adisa et al (2021) noted that positive organizational behaviour is exhibited through punctuality to work, attendance, adhering to rule, discipline and good conduct of employees in an organization. Similarly, Ughamadu, Ezeaku and Nwogbo (2024a) maintained that organizational behaviour is exhibited by teachers through their punctuality, showing strong passion for engaging in instructional tasks, working hard to execute delegated tasks, developing mutual relationship with members of staff, obeying professional code of conduct and according respect to the constituted authority.

However, there are some teachers who tend to display undesirable organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Ughamadu, et al (2024a) noted that some teachers absent themselves from school without fair reasons, go late to school and engage in different forms of professional misconducts. This assertion is supported by the observation made by Obi et al (2022) that there are incidences of unacceptable behaviours, absenteeism, lateness to school, teachers doing private business at official time, and loitering of staff in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Teachers' undesirable behaviour could be attributed to laxities in managerial competencies of principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To buttress this, Ughamadu, Ezeaku and Nwogbo (2024b) noted that there are cases of absenteeism, uncooperative attitude, persistent lateness, laziness in the workplace, unauthorized movement of teachers from their duty post and poor commitment to teaching secondary school students due to incompetency of the principals. Continuing, Ughamadu et al maintained that there are distrust and unhealthy interpersonal relationships among staff which tend to hinder teamwork and good organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Okekeocha and Ezinine (2021) that some principals lack manner of approach to teachers, fail to recognize the outstanding performance of staff, hardly involve teachers in decision-making and impose their authority on the teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against this background that this study investigated principals' managerial competencies as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Principals are required to possess and apply unique sets of managerial competencies such as decision-making and motivation to enable them succeed in managerial roles of managing the behaviour of teachers. Unfortunately, some teachers seem to be neglected in taking crucial decisions and even when they are consulted, their opinions are disregarded by principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Outstanding achievement of some teachers appears to go unappreciated and unrecognized by these principals forcing teachers to display undesirable behaviour.

Teachers tend to reciprocate undesirable attitude of principals through negative organizational behaviour. Some of these undesirable behaviours appear to be reflected in form of rampant late coming to work, absenteeism and aiding examination malpractice. There are also some teachers who tend to deliberately avoid staff meetings, loiter around the school during their lesson periods and engage in private businesses during working hours. The State Government through educational agencies, board and ministries have made substantial efforts to remedy the situations through training programmes for principals to improve their managerial competences for promoting good teachers' organizational behaviour. If the current situation is not improved, the attainment of the ultimate goal of

secondary education will be in jeopardy. The students will not acquire the essential skills and knowledge required to make meaning contributions to the growth and development of Anambra State. These problems prompted the researcher to investigate principals' managerial competencies as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine principals' managerial competencies as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. Principals' decision-making competency as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' motivational competency as correlate of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' motivational competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' motivational competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Anambra State which is one of the five states in South-Eastern Nigeria. The choice of Anambra State for the study is informed by the fact that some teachers exhibit absenteeism and engage in other forms of professional misconducts probably due to some principals are incompetent in rational making decision and motivating them. The population of the study comprised 269 principals in the 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Census sampling technique was used to enable the use of all 269 principals for the study. All the 269 principals were used for the study because the manageable and relatively size of the population.

Two sets of instruments titled "Principals' Managerial Competencies Scale (PMCS)" and "Teachers' Organizational Behaviour Scale (TOBS)" were used for data collection. The two sets of the instruments were structured by the researcher based on insight gained from literature and consultation with experts. MCS was designed to elicit information on principals' managerial competencies. The instrument contained 23 items spread in four clusters I and II. Cluster I which focused on decision-making competency contains eight items and Cluster II contained 15 items on motivational competency. Those items are placed on a four-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. TOBS was structured to measure teachers' organizational behaviour. The instrument contains 21 items structured on a four-point rating of four-point

rating of Always (A), Seldom (S), Rarely (R) and Never (N), weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. A copy of the instruments is attached as Appendix C on page 139. The face validity of the instruments was determined by three experts, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation Unit) all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instruments used for data collection. Cronbach alpha method involving single administration of instruments was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The scores obtained from the 40 teachers in the trial testing of the instrument were used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument using Cronbach Alpha method which yielded coefficient values of 0.77 and 0.84 for four clusters of PMCS with the overall reliability index being 0.81. On the other hand, coefficient of 0.84 was obtained for TOBS.

Direct delivery method was used by the researcher and five research assistants for data collection. A total of 269 copies of the instruments were distributed to principal and 261 copies of questionnaires (97%) were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. For the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient recommended by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Interpretation
.00- .19	Weak Relationship
.20- .39	Fair Relationship
.40- .69	Moderate Relationship
.70- .89	Strong Relationship
.90-.99	Very Strong Relationship
1	Perfect

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if the obtained p-value is equal to or greater than the significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected but if obtained p-value is less than the significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected. All data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.

Result

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson (r) on the Summary of Pearson (r) on Relationship between Principals' Decision-Making Competency and Teachers' Organizational Behaviour

Variables	N	Principals' Decision-Making Competency	Teachers' Organizational Behaviour	Remarks
Principals' Decision-Making Competency	261	1.00	.724	Strong
Teachers' Organizational Behaviour	261	.724	1.00	

Table 1 reveals that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.724 was obtained. This shows that there is strong relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This indicated that the increase in principals' decision-making competency will strongly improve teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: The Summary of Pearson (p-value) on Significant Relationship between Principals' Decision-Making Competency and Teachers' Organizational Behaviour

Variables	N	Principals' Decision-Making Competency	Teachers' Organizational Behavior	P -value	α	Remarks
Principals' Decision-Making Competency	261	1.00	.724	.000	.05	Rejected
Teachers' Organizational Behaviour	261	.724	1.00			

As shown in Table 2, the p -value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between principals' decision-making competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals' motivational competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson (r) on the Summary of Pearson (r) on Relationship between Principals' Motivational Competency and Teachers' Organizational Behaviour

Variables	N	Principals' Motivational Competency	Teachers' Organizational Behaviour	Remarks
Principals' Motivational Competency	261	1.00	.734	Strong
Teachers' Organizational Behaviour	261	.734	1.00	

Result in Table 3 indicates that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.734 was obtained. This shows that there is strong relationship between principals' motivational competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This indicated that the principals' motivational competency can strongly contribute to teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between principals’ motivational competency and teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of Pearson (p-value) on Significant Relationship between Principals’ Motivational Competency and Teachers’ Organizational Behaviour

Variables	N	Principals’ Motivational Competency	Teachers’ Organizational Behavior	P-value	α	Remarks
Principals’ Motivational Competency	261	1.00	.734	.000	.05	Rejected
Teachers’ Organizational Behaviour	261	.734	1.00			

Table 4 shows that the *p*-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, since the *p*-value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between principals’ decision-making competency and teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The result of the study indicated that there was a strong relationship between principals’ decision-making competency and teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The possible reason for this finding is that decision-making competency enables principals to define desirable organizational behaviour expected of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Abdullah and Rahaman (2020) which showed that there was a strong relationship between decision-making competency and organizational behaviour in public secondary schools. The agreement between the findings could be attributed to the similarity in level of education in which the studies were conducted.

Principals’ decision-making competency enable them to take into account multiple perspectives in finding solution to negative work attitude of staff so as to strongly improve teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is through decision-making competency that principals make rational and informed decisions and rules that guide conduct of teachers which might account for strong relationship with their organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Further result showed that there is significant relationship between principals’ decision-making competency and teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This upheld the finding of Abdullah and Rahaman (2020) which showed that there was a significant relationship between decision-making competency and organizational behaviour in public secondary schools. The principals who decision-making competency can analyze the problems of teachers, identify and choose the best alternative to solve them to encourage positive organization behaviour.

The finding of the study indicated that there was a strong relationship between principals’ motivational competency and teachers’ organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The finding could be explained by the fact that motivational competency of principals is the means of recognizing and appreciating the efforts of teachers which make them happy in the work environment and thereby exhibit positive organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed

with the finding of Mashaqbah (2018) which revealed that there was a strong relationship between motivational competency and organizational behaviour among teachers of public schools. This refuted the finding of Udrescu and Gheorghe (2017) who reported that there was moderate relationship between motivational competency and organizational behaviour of staff. The difference in time span of eight years can be associated with changes that could account for the disagreement between the findings. It is through motivational competency that principals support, encourage and boost the morale of teachers to display strong organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Teachers who are motivated with praises, gifts, awards and promotion feel valued and thereby reciprocate the gesture by displaying strong organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

It was also showed that there is significant relationship between principals' motivational competency and teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This supported the finding of Mashaqbah (2018) which revealed that there was a significant relationship between motivational competency and organizational behaviour among teachers of public schools. It is through principals' motivational competency that health work environment is created which thereby account for the significant relationship with teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Motivated teachers are more committed, engaged and willing to exhibit significant organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that principals' managerial competencies have positive and significant correlation with teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. However, the magnitude of the correlations found are strong, indicating that managerial competencies of principals can substantially contribute to teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Principals who possess managerial competencies of decision-making and motivation can positively induce teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Education should offer annual financial supports to principals for period of at least two years to enable them enroll in short leadership courses on decision-making competency to refresh their knowledge of making informed decisions that facilitate organizational behaviour of teachers.
2. Principals should improve in the application motivational competency through recognizing outstanding staff at the end of every month and also yearly award for excellence ceremony to appreciate teachers for their positive contributions to school so as to enhance their organizational behaviour.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, M.S., and Rahaman, S, (2020). Relationship between decision-making competency (skills) and organizational behaviour management. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*, 10(14), 246-257.
- Adiotomre, U.L. (2025). Principals' instructional leadership styles and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 13(1), 1-6.
- Adisa, A.Y., Suleiman, Y., Ishola, M.A., and Muchilwa, E.H. (2021). Relationship between workplace behaviour and staff job performance in private secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education in Black Sea Region*, 7(1), 16-31.
- Agbo, E.N. and Eleberi, D.G. (2025). Secondary education and values re-orientation in secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 13(1), 1- 8.
- Alsagr, A.M. (2021). Remarks on the use of Pearson's and Spearman's correlation in assessing relationships in ophthalmic data. *African Vision and Eye Health*, 80(1), 1-10.
- Eze, O.U. (2024). Principals' managerial competencies as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 7(1), 146-152.
- Ibezim, M.C. (2024). Principals' managerial competences as correlate of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 7(4), 69-79.
- Mashaqbah, N.K. (2018). Relationship between motivational competency and organizational behaviour among teachers of public schools in Mafraq Province of Jordan. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(31), 224-239.
- Obi, H.C., Ogbunude, M.I. and Chukwudolue, A.C. (2022). Influence of principals' managerial competences on the performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *COOU Journal of Educational Research*, 7(1), 462-471.
- Odu-Dikoro, T. (2022). Principals' managerial competencies and teachers' job effectiveness in public and private secondary schools in Delta State. *Scholarly Journal of Management Sciences Research*, 1(7), 44-64.
- Okafor, P.C., Nnebedum, C. and Oshia, E.C. (2025a). Work-life balance and job security practices as correlates of teachers' job performance in private secondary schools in Anambra State. *Journal of Frontiers in Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(1), 271-276.
- Okafor, P.C., Nnebedum, C. and Oshia, E.C. (2025b). Challenges and measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Research*, 12(5), 630-640.

- Okekeocha, N.C. and Ezinine, R.U. (2021). Interpersonal relationship competency as correlates of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(2), 121-129.
- Oredein, A.O. and Opatunde, A.F. (2023). Decision-making skills and public senior secondary school principals' administrative effectiveness in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 20(4), 32-44.
- Pacino, M.B. and Baguio, J.B. (2024). Organizational behaviour and workplace environment of technology and livelihood education (TLE) teachers in public secondary school. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 50(11), 349-356.
- Samancı, O. and Mazlumoglu, M (2023). Decision-making skill: How to make better ecisions? *Türk Akademik Yayınlar Dergisi (TAY Journal)*, 7(2), 668-683.
- Udrescu and Gheorghe (2017). Motivational competency and organizational behaviour: Staff between value added and conflict-generating losses. *Academic Journal of Economic Studies*, 3(2), 55-59.
- Ughamadu, U. Ezeaku, S.N. and Nwogbo, M.O. (2024a). Organizational justice as predictor of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Education and National Development*, 2(1), 1-14.
- Wordah, E., and Ekwesianya, A.A. (2020). Principalship, decision-making and teachers' job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *Global Journal of Education, Humanities and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 134-143.
- Ughamadu, U., Ezeaku, S.N. and Nwogbo, M.O. (2024b). Total quality management practices as predictors of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*. 10(3), 12-24.